

INDOMITABLE WOMEN

A (his)tory of audiovisual contemporary art created by 85 women from 1944 to 2009.

Curated by **Macu Moran**, 2010

Presented at:

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Exhibited at:

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Special thanks to the pioneer artists whose support has made *Indomitable Women* possible:

Historic Cut:

Maya Deren / Dara Birnbaum / Carolee Schneeman / Judy Chicago / Yoko Ono / Beryl Korot / VALIE EXPORT / Joan Jonas / Ana Bella Geiger / Colette / Orlan / Marisa González / Guerrilla Girls / Ximena Cuevas / Joan Logue / Suzanne Lacy / Lynn Hershman / Paloma Navares / Tracey Moffat / Coco Fusco / Terry Berkovitz / Amy Greenfield / Angie Bonino / Maria Fernanda Cardoso / Mariko Mori / Martha Rosler / Beth Moyses / Dora García / Jenny Marketou / Ana de Alvear / Sigalit Landau

Contemporary Cut:

Ester Achaerandio / Grimanesa Amoros / Paula Anta / Carmen Arrabal / Gloria Arteaga / Cristina Artola / Lidia Benavides / Patricia Betancur / Roxanne Billamboz / Raquel Bravo / Johanna Bruckner / Patricia Bueno / Laura Celada / Marcela Cernadas / Izumi Chiaraluce / Maria Jose Chinchilla / Heroínas de la Cultura / Ana de Matos / Begoña Egurbide / Carmen Esplá / Mari Carmen García Maheredo / Regina Jose Galindo / Chus Garcia Fraile / Amparo Garrido / Nuria Gil / Anna Gimein / Heide Hatry / Olga Kisseleva / Hye Rim Lee / Jin Lee-Kyung / Glenda León / Francesca Llopis / Laila Lobo / Cristina Martin Lara / Sabine Massenet / Laura Mergoni / Macu Moran / Post Op / Funda Ozgunaydin / Teresa Puppo / Gabriela Larrañaga / Graciela Taquini / Enriqueta Rocher / Eva Rohweder / Alejandra Rotondi / Lorena Mendez / Ana Luisa Sanchez-Law / Eva Sanchez / Dafna Shalom / Jacklyn Soo / Evelyn Stermitz / Rosalin Suero Castillo / Mariana Vassileva

“Passion does not soften the light of intelligence, but rather overexcites it, providing it with a particular precognition, and extraordinary subtleness and ingeniousness.”

- Charles Malapert (1581-1630)

INDOMITABLE WOMEN, Curator Essay:

The **Indomitable Women** selection certainly attests to a passionate process, through proposals and reflections developed with the necessary wisdom to allow total freedom of creation under diverse circumstances. Artists passionate to leave their singular imprint, fearlessly redefining contemporary aesthetics and thought.

They are indomitable because both endogenous and exogenous domination mechanisms have not worked on them. They are indomitable because no one has been able to cast them into a mold designed through a long history developed for and by men; immune to the standard guidelines, the product of mental paradigms that come from unconscious beliefs and implicit cultural values that restrain creativity and repress ideas, towards obedient acquiescence to the predominant masculine role, established in most societies since the origins of humankind.

Indomitable, once again, because of embracing the audiovisual medium, embodying the temporal dimension as an active player in the universe of perceptions and multiplying the experience with countless visual impacts, which choreograph on the retina an everlasting sensation. Passionate women who know how to let time do its work in their artistic praxis, who have not been stopped by the recalcitrant resistance of conservative reactionaries afraid of change and specific to each generation. Women with their own voice and criteria, who, by vocation, have let their imagination fly and take us all towards new futures, conceived for an advanced, dynamic and multi-faceted society.

This show is an effort to discover the characteristics of the point of view of women behind the camera as a pertinent discursive thread that has not been sufficiently analyzed, exhibited or recognized. It invites a reflection upon the perception and vital sensibility that defines the various approaches of the female creative nature and, on a deeper level, concerns anchored in the psyche over time, perceptible thanks to a transhistorical lens.

Gathering works developed within the past seven decades, the selection attempts to glimpse that *ethereal something* that is a backdrop to women’s artistic praxis, always loyal to the duty of evolution inherent in art and aligned with its revolutionary power. Art is here distinguished as a confluence of currents of thought that promotes the creation of innovative notions, which subtly filter through society. Meanings and signifiers that have created and continue to create their imprints in contemporary art history, confronting times past and generating new ideas and original perspectives.

The flux of consciousness that emanates from these works is an intimate monologue of oscillating thought, images, wishes, emotions, curiosities and reflections, containing surprising conceptual, aesthetic and, of course, technical and technological connections. Works elaborated with the virtuosity that only passion can conceive, and that in the act of decoding offers an open reading to the viewers, allowing them to have an intimate relationship to the codes and sub-codes proposed in each work by this splendid group of artists and *indomitable women*.

What it is, will not remain; what it was, is not any longer. Intrinsicly bound to change, time does not stop; neither does it repeat itself. Wise are those creators who have an inspiring muse and travel companion in this *callida iunctura*.

Macu Moran, 2009

Indomitable Women within the early history of feminist exhibitions:

Gathering 84 women artists from all over the world who with their work continue redefining contemporary aesthetics and thought, the show *Indomitable Women* built upon and continue the legacy of key shows that attempted to assemble feminist art practices across geographies, mediums, and conceptual frames.

To position it within earlier feminist curatorial legacy, we should start with the point at which curating distinctly emerged as a way to expose structural exclusions within institutions. A significant historical reference is found 40 years earlier in the **Aldrich Contemporary Art Museum's** with **Lucy R. Lippard's** exhibition *Twenty-Six Contemporary Women Artists* (April–June 1971) a fieldwork overview of women artists active in New York during early 70s.

As cited by **The Aldrich Contemporary Art Museum**, **Lippard** stated: “*I accepted this exhibition because I recognized that numerous women artists created work that rivaled, or surpassed, what was on display, but due to the persistent discriminatory practices of most galleries and museums, few people are likely to visit their studios or regard them as seriously as their male counterparts*”. A central curatorial statement that identifies institutional discrimination as a reality influencing access, visibility, and significance.

Lippard's introduction rejects a simplistic essentialism regarding *women's art* while still affirming a significant political and perceptual distinction that necessitates new interpretive approaches. It refers to institutional discrimination not as an abstraction, but as a concrete condition shaping access, visibility, and seriousness. **Lippard** anticipated a body of art history and criticism that will be more suited to women's sensibilities, while also rejecting inane clichés of 'feminine' art grounded in superficial stylistic traits.

From this early institutional intervention, a second crucial strand in the same lineage is the emergence of video as a medium in which women could define new artistic languages, not sufficiently analyzed, exhibited or recognized. A direct anchor for this claim appears in **JoAnn Hanley**'s curatorial framing of 35 works for the show *The First Generation: Women and Video, 1970–75*.

The demands of new interpretive tools, within the tension between rejecting reductive stereotypes and insisting that patriarchal norms constrain creativity, mirrors the conceptual architecture of the Indomitable Women statement of artists immune to the standard guidelines, not because they conform to a single “women’s style,” but because they refuse the paradigms that attempt to cast them into a historically masculine mold.

Hanley describes the period as perhaps, the first time that men and women artists worked in a medium on equal footing, emphasizing that without the burdens of tradition linked with other media, women video artists were freer to concentrate on process, often using video to explore the body and the self through autobiography and examinations of gendered identity.

Hanley's show ties early women’s video to both aesthetic innovation and political critique, noting that women used the new medium to create social and political analyses of the myths and facts of patriarchal culture, revealing the socioeconomic realities and political ideologies that dominated everyday life.

In this sense, women’s videoart is not only resilient as biography, but also a set of formal strategies that turns the camera toward the self, using the body and voice as material, reworking the temporality of viewing, and challenging the ideological guidelines that structure perception. Women artists embraced the audiovisual medium by making temporality an active player in the universe of perceptions, because it frames the medium’s relative newness not only as a technical shift, but as an opening in cultural authority.

Hanley quotes critic **Martha Gevers**, stating that women artists used video to propose a redefinition of *reality* by asserting the validity of women’s existence and experiences, by challenging accepted ideas about those experiences or by a combination of both strategies.

Women’s video practices redefined the very idea of reality, a theme that can be woven into your language of perception, retina, and time. **Hanley** demonstrates women’s foundational role in early video art and provides a medium-specific account of how video enabled autobiography, body-based inquiry, and critiques of patriarchal culture. The audiovisual medium becomes a choreographer of perception, an apparatus through which lived experience is not merely represented but actively re-validated against dominant cultural scripts.

Through the series of seminal shows exhibited from 1994 to 1996, *Inside the Visible: An Elliptical Traverse of 20th-century Art* from the Artforum event archive, curator M. **Catherine de Zegher** presented over 250 works by 37 women artists spanning Europe, Asia, North and South America. According to Koslow Miller, the exhibition suggested a trajectory of invisible artistic production that runs parallel to the predominant art-historical axis, stating how women's praxis persist across time as an under-acknowledged continuity, perceptible when one reads across decades rather than through a single canonical line.

The show was not organized chronologically but divided into sections drawing from three politically and socially volatile periods of the 20th century, building associations of ideas and images across time. The interest was not in creating a simple timeline, but to reveal recurring gestures, shared refusals, and evolving media tactics through which women artists have not been stopped by conservative resistance across generations.

Indomitable Women show also continues with the effort of the exhibition *WACK! Art and the Feminist Revolution* presented at the Museum of Contemporary Art, Los Angeles from March 4–July 16, 2007, and notes that it later traveled to the National Museum of Women in the Arts (Sept–Dec 2007) and PS1 Contemporary Art Center (Feb–May 2008), featuring works from 120 artists and artists' groups from around the world. An exhibition that surveyed work across media and was organized in themes including “Body as Medium,” “Gender Performance,” “Knowledge as Power,” and “Making Art History,” among others.

An assertion into a historically grounded continuation of a long-standing feminist curatorial mandate: to make visible what institutions have structurally failed to see. Another great example of institutional resistance, pushing to exhibit the aesthetics of time, and the need for recognition, ensuring that the intellectual stakes remain consistent with their own language: freedom under diverse circumstances, resistance to domination, and the temporal intelligence of audiovisual form.

References:

- *Twenty-Six Contemporary Women Artists*. [The Aldrich Contemporary Art Museum, 1971](#).
- *The First Generation: Women and Video, 1970–75*. [Independent Curators International, 1993](#) and [JoAnn Hanley, excerpt from catalogue essay, 1993](#).
- Koslow Miller, F. (1996). “Inside the Visible” (Artforum event archive entry describing the exhibition's scope, structure, and aims). [Artforum Archive](#).
- *WACK! Art and the Feminist Revolution*. [Wikipedia WACK! Art and the Feminist Revolution](#).

FULL LIST OF WORKS:

1. **Joan Jonas:** Glass Puzzle, 1974, 17'27", Japan/U.S.A
2. **Beryl Korot:** Lost Lascaux bull, 1973, 4'10", U.S.A.
3. **Martha Rosler:** Chile on The Road to NAFTA, 1997, 10'00", U.S.A.
4. **Beth Moyses:** Dia a Dia, 1998-1999, 6'52", Brazil
5. **Rosalin Suero Castillo:** Drag Line, 2006, 1'26", Panama
6. **Glenda Leon:** Inner Sea, 2006, 1'20", Cuba
7. **Teresa Puppo, Gabriela Larrañaga, Graciela Taquini:** Secrets, 2007, 5'00", Uruguay/Argentina
8. **Dora Garcia:** Heartbeat, 1999, 5'24", Spain
9. **Patricia Betancur:** Yo amo..., 2008, 5'00", Uruguay
10. **Carmen Arrabal:** Troublee / Tsunami, 2009, 4'53", Spain
11. **Raquel Bravo:** Scenario#2, 2008, 5'00", Spain
12. **Begoña Egurbide:** Silent Room, 2007, 3'19", Spain
13. **Tracey Moffat:** Heaven, 1990, 28'00", Australia
14. **Maya Deren:** At Land, 1944, 15'17", Ukraine/U.S.A.
15. **Yoko Ono:** Freedom, 1972, 60", Japan / U.S.A.
16. **Guerrilla Girls:** Guerrilla Girls, 1985-2007, 3'30", U.S.A.
17. **Ximena Cuevas:** Before T.V., 1985, 1' 43", Mexico
18. **Joan Logue:** 30 Second Portraits, 1980, 6' 01", U.S.A.
19. **Marisa Gonzalez:** Domestic scene with a green worm, 1984, 7'15", Spain
20. **Paloma Navares:** Els banyets, 1987, 1'40", Spain
21. **Angie Bonino:** The Wall, 1996, 1'30", Peru/Italy
22. **Suzanne Lacy:** Learn where the meat comes from, 1976, 14'25", U.S.A.
23. **Ana de Alvear:** Mood Landscapes Reloaded, 1998, 3'00", Spain
24. **Anna Gimein:** Maria, 2007, 4'08", Russia/U.S.A./Spain
25. **Amparo Garrido:** Don't say anything, 2008, 2'37", Spain
26. **Chus Garcia-Fraile:** Running, 2009, 2'43", Spain
27. **Beatriz Caravaggio:** Interview with a white man, 2009, 1'20", Spain
28. **Carmen Espla:** Rain, 2007, 3'00", Spain
29. **VALIE EXPORT:** Remote... Remote..., 1973, 9'55" Austria
30. **Gloria Arteaga:** Recycle city, 2007, 5'00", Peru
31. **Marcela Cernadas:** Rosa, 2008, 1'07", Argentina
32. **J.K. Lee:** Total Music I & II, 2006, 4'46", South Korea
33. **Patricia Bueno:** Yours is the Kingdom, 2007, 5'00", Peru
34. **Alejandra Rotondi, Lorena Mendez:** Female Things, 2009, 3'11", Argentina
35. **Nuria Gil:** Latidoamerica, 2008, 3'35", Spain

36. **Grimanesa Amoros**: Preoccupation, 2008, 1'22", Peru/U.S.A.
37. **Sigalit Landau**: Three man hula, 1999, 1'36", Israel
38. **Carolee Schneemann**: Fuses, 1964-1967, 29'51", U.S.A.
39. **Francesca Llopis**: The virtue of giving me comfort, 2007, 5'00", Spain
40. **Johanna Bruckner**: The Gestual Abject: Myspasedotcom, 2009, 5'00", Germany
41. **Maria Jose Chinchilla**: Transformation, 2008, 5'00", Spain
42. **Judy Chicago**: Atmospheres, 1969-1974, 14'21", U.S.A.
43. **Laura Mergoni**: Tombola, 2009, 4'05", Italy
44. **Hye Rim Lee**: Crystal City Spun, 2007, 3'15", Korea
45. **Post Op**: Implants, 2006, 5'00", Spain
46. **Jacklyn Soo**: Songs of innocence, 2008, 3'15", Singapore
47. **Ana De_Matos**: King Racing Girls, 2007, 2'44", Spain
48. **Macu Moran**: When wild instincts revive, predator sharpens the knife, 2007, 4'00", Spain
49. **Laia Lobo (Montse Pujantell)**: Séquiéneres (autoportrait in color), 2007, 3'00", Spain
50. **Roxanne Billamboz**: How to disappear brightly, 2007, 4'25", France
51. **Colette**: Justine and the boys, 1979, 18' 13", Tunizia / U.S.A.
52. **Lidia Benavides**: Galactoforo, 2007, 4'47", Spain
53. **Heroínas de la Cultura**: Notes from Never Land, 2007, 5'00", Spain
54. **Laura Celada**: Anubis (a mith de_construction), 2009, 4'57", Spain
55. **Enriqueta Rocher**: Under the skin, 2009, 4'32", Spain
56. **Olga Kisseleva**: My double Life, 2008, 2'57", Russia
57. **Cristina Martin Lara**: Landpartie If, 2008, 1'40", Spain
58. **Sabine Massenet**: Bande Annonce, 2009, 4'06", France
59. **Coco Fusco**: The Couple in the Cage: A Guatinaui, 1993, 31'00", Cuba/U.S.A.
60. **Amy Greenfield**: MuselC of the BODY, 1994, 10'20", U.S.A.
61. **Heide Hatry**: Expectations, 2007, 2'47", Germany
62. **Ebba Rohweder**: Intervention I, 2009, 2'21", Germany
63. **Mariana Vassileva**: Definition, 2006, 2'10", Bulgaria / Germany
64. **Orlan**: Mesurage du Musee Saint-Pierre, 1979, 17'30", France
65. **Funda Ozgunaydin**: Displacement of culturalself, 2008, 4'10", Turkey
66. **Mari Carmen Garcia Maheredo**: Paiting Nature, 2008, 3'05", Spain
67. **Evelin Stermitz**: Table Talk, 2008, 2'34", Austria
68. **Ester Achaerandio**: Entre-vista, 2007, 5'00", Spain
69. **Cristina Artola**: Ages and Death, 2008, 4'26", Spain
70. **Lynn Hershman**: Confessions of a Chamaleon, 1986, 10'00", U.S.A.
71. **Terry Berkowitz**: Backseat, 1994, 21' 49", U.S.A.
72. **Maria Fernanda Cardoso**: Cardoso Flea Circus, 1996, 8'00", Colombia
73. **Paula Anta**: Risoletto, 2007, 4'30", Spain

74. **Dafna Shalom:** Arvit (Evening pray), 2008, 4'23", Israel
75. **Regina Jose Galindo:** Confession, 2007, 2'22", Guatemala
76. **Ana Bella Geiger:** Passages Passagens, 1974, 9'30", Brazil
77. **Ana Luisa Sanchez-Laws:** Navigator, 2009, 3'13", Panama
78. **Jenny Marketou:** Dear Lady M., 1995-2009, 3'59", Greece
79. **Dara Birnbaum:** Canon: Taking to the Street, 1990, 10'00", U.S.A.
80. **Eva Sanchez:** Yo no soy bonita, ni lo quiero ser, 2009, 2'05", Spain
81. **Izumi Chiaraluce:** Lou, 2009, 5'00", Japan/Italy
82. **Mariko Mori:** Miko No Inori, 1996, 14'50", Japan